

SAMPLE VALUES OF TOTAL DOSE CONFERRED TO PATIENTS IN STUDY

Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) guidance is helpful
in reducing dose exposure to pediatric patients undergoing
radiofrequency ablation of osteoid osteoma

Francesco Fiore¹ · Francesco Somma² · Roberto D'Angelo¹ · Luca Tarotto¹ · Vincenzo Stoia²

Radiologia Interventistica, Istituto Nazionale Tumori IRCCS "Fond. G. Pascale"- NAPOLI

Ospedale del Mare, A.S.L. Napoli 1, NAPOLI

PATIENTS	D.o.T.	total DLP (mGy)
F.E.	11/06/2016	337.21
N.P.	17/05/2017	475.40
A.R.	19/03/2018	1358.88
C.L.M.	02/08/2018	610.07
M.M.	07/11/2019	541.6
G.A.	05/12/2019	469.2